

REUSE AND REPAIR OF ELECTRICAL AND ELECTRONIC EQUIPMENT

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to analyze how circular economy procedures help reuse WEEE and identify the factors that led to the generation of waste electrical and electronic equipment during COVID-19.

The methodology applied in this work is the method of qualitative analysis of the secondary data from the specialized literature, based on the criteria for elaborating a systematic theoretical review in order to map the existing knowledge regarding the evaluation of the reuse and repair of waste electrical and electronic equipment

Findings A total of 48 scientific articles were published between 2017 and 2022. The articles were identified based on appropriate sets of keywords and terms: reuse, circular economy, repair. Following the filters applied, such as the type of document, and the Web of science category, there are a number of 21 articles left that have been analyzed yourself

Research limitations/implications The literature contains a fairly small number of reports on the management and life-cycle extension of electrical and electronic waste

Practical implications This method of reusing waste electrical and electronic equipment allows the product to retain its economic value for as long as possible, thus helping both the social and the economic environment

Originality/value The most effective end-of-life option for waste electric and electronic equipments is reuse, a good option for environmental impact and socio-economic benefits. Thus, following these analyzed articles, measures are recommended to improve the management of waste electrical and electronic equipment at a global level, more precisely the inclusion of the principles of the circular economy in the production of electrical and electronic equipment.

Key words: E-waste, reuse, circular economy, repair, end-of-life.

Introduction

The dynamization of the urbanization process, the community of consumers, the growth of the global population, the development of information and communication technology, the incessant development of the living standards, the reduction of the life cycle of products, all these have contributed since the end of the XX th century, to the amplification of the volume and the branching of waste streams. As regards the sudden minimization of natural resources, the rapid degradation of soil, air, water quality and the deterioration of natural ecosystems, international interests in waste management have taken on great importance in identifying the best and safest solutions and technologies for waste management

In this situation, waste management has become a real substantive issue in terms of future socio-economic development, a direct consequence of a present economic development of a linear type. One of the special categories, with a high degree of difficulty in terms of capitalization, is given by electrical and electronic equipment. This waste has been nominated as the fastest growing waste globally (Menikpura, Santo, Hotta, 2014; Islam et. al., 2016; Shittu, Williams, Shaw, 2021), thanks to the growth of industrialization and digitization.

The outbreak of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in 2019 has changed the direction of events globally. This disease has had major consequences for all sectors of the economy, including the educational, health and environmental sectors. The imposition of lockdowns and quarantines has caused humanity to make more and more use of technology and also TIC equipment, as schools have taken online courses. The increased use of these devices is not without environmental consequences. Some of the likely challenges are the increased import of electronic waste (e-waste) in the form of used electronic devices and the challenge of disposing of these devices once they reach the end-of-life stage and become waste.

Global E-waste Monitor 2020, published an announcement saying that in 2019, 53.6 million Mt of waste electrical and electronic equipment was generated, resulting in a total of 7.3 kg per capita. However, it is estimated that the overall amount of waste electrical and electronic equipment will increase by 2 Mt per year. Unfortunately, specialists estimate that the global quantity will exceed 74 Mt in 2030.

Thus the role of the circular economy is to maximize resource efficiency by keeping materials at the highest value, which can be achieved by reusing, reconditioning, remanufacturing products (Lakatos et al., 2018). When the product is maintained for as long as possible on the market, then the product has the highest level of efficiency, so it requires the prioritization of reuse (Rada, Cioca, Ionescu, 2017)

The extension of the service life of a product is given by the reuse of waste equipment and its components.

The reuse action means the recovery of the product at the end-of-use stage and its reintroduction on the market. (Cioca et al., 2015)

The EU's circular material utilization rate (so-called the circularity rate) in 2020 reached 12.8% which means that almost 13% of the material resources used in the EU come from recycled or repaired waste. One of the main barriers that stand in the way of reuse is the way products are collected after they are thrown away at the end of their lives. These items shall be considered as waste before they are recovered. These products processed in this way end up damaged and their reuse value is small or not at all. The first step in a process of preparing for reuse begins with sorting the items to select the items that are ready for reuse, this process is done through a visual inspection, applying a safety test and a functionality test after this process follows the deletion of the data from the device and then the device is disassembled, cleaned and repaired.

This work emphasizes the most significant publications in the field of reference of electrical and electronic equipment. The study's goal is to examine the role that circular economy practices have in WEEE reusing.

Methodology

This study addresses a method of qualitative analysis of secondary data from the literature, based on the criteria for developing a systematic theoretical review. Thus, the process developed by Kitchenham (2004) of systematizing previous empirical results was followed, applying the following steps: (1) planning - motivation and protocol; (2) conducting the review - identification the research, selecting the primary researches, appreciating the value of the researches, filtering the data, and the last phase (3) describing the effects of the review. To identify the relevant studies, appropriate sets of keywords and terms were used: reuse, circular economy, repair.

These research models, which contain topics related to the reuse and repair of waste electrical and electronic equipment, are usually published in journals that have as main topics the environment, sustainability and sustainability and also waste management. The vast majority of the articles analyzed most often refer to three processes such as collecting, preparing for reuse and redistributing them.

To begin with, a total of 48 scientific articles were identified following the assignment of keywords. The first filter applied was the one represented by the year of publications, the interval 2017 and 2022 was chosen. As a result of this filter, 46 items remained. The second filter selected was the document type filter, where only the items as a document type were selected and 34 items remained by selection.

The last filter applied was the one represented by the category Web of science where we chose the categories Environmental Engineering Environmental Sciences, Technology Green Sustainable

Science, Environmental Studies following this filter remained a number of 21 articles relevant to our studies.

Table 1 lists the 21 articles that have been studied in depth and figure 1 shows the number of articles published per year, where in 2021, following the selections, 5 articles were published, in 2020 4 articles were published and in 2017, 2018, 2019, 2022 3 articles were published each.

Table 1. Studied articles

2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	2017
Andersen, T. (2022). A comparative study of national variations of the European WEEE directive: manufacturer's view. <i>Environmental Science and Pollution Research</i> , 29(14), 19920-19939.	Pérez-Martínez, M. M., Carrillo, C., Rodeiro-Iglesias, J., & Soto, B. (2021). Life cycle assessment of repurposed waste electric and electronic equipment in comparison with original equipment. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 27, 1637-1649.	Johnson, M., McMahon, K., & Fitzpatrick, C. (2020). A preparation for reuse trial of washing machines in Ireland. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(3), 1175.	Cole, C., Gnanapragasam, A., Cooper, T., & Singh, J. (2019). An assessment of achievements of the WEEE Directive in promoting movement up the waste hierarchy: experiences in the UK. <i>Waste Management</i> , 87, 417-427.	Zacho, K. O., Bundgaard, A. M., & Mosgaard, M. A. (2018). Constraints and opportunities for integrating preparation for reuse in the Danish WEEE management system. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , 138, 13-23.	Parajuly, K., & Wenzel, H. (2017). Potential for circular economy in household WEEE management. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 151, 272-285.
Peiró, L. T., Fernández, B. G., & Durany, X. G. (2022). Investigating a repair workshop: The reuse of washing machines in Barcelona. <i>Sustainable Production and Consumption</i> , 29, 171-179.	Hischier, R., & Böni, H. W. (2021). Combining environmental and economic factors to evaluate the reuse of electrical and electronic equipment—a Swiss case study. <i>Resources, Conservation and Recycling</i> , 166, 105307.	Boldoczki, S., Thorenz, A., & Tuma, A. (2020). The environmental impacts of preparation for reuse: A case study of WEEE reuse in Germany. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 252, 119736.	Messmann, L., Boldoczki, S., Thorenz, A., & Tuma, A. (2019). Potentials of preparation for reuse: A case study at collection points in the German state of Bavaria. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 211, 1534-1546.	Bonoli, A., Dolci, N., Foschi, E., Lalli, F., Prandstraller, D., & Zanni, S. (2018). End Of Service Scenario For Universities' Informatic Equipment: Recovery And Repair As Educational And Research Tool For Circular Economy And Urban Mining. <i>Multidisciplinary Journal for Waste Resources & Residues</i> , 4, 90-97.	Parajuly, K., & Wenzel, H. (2017). Product family approach in e-waste management: a conceptual framework for circular economy. <i>Sustainability</i> , 9(5), 768.
Rudolf, S., Blömeke, S., Niemeyer, J. F., Lawrenz, S., Sharma, P., Hemminghaus, S., ... & Herrmann, C. (2022). Extending the Life Cycle of EEE—Findings from a Repair Study in Germany: Repair Challenges and	Shittu, O. S., Williams, I. D., Shaw, P., Montiero, N., & Crefield, R. (2021). Demonstrating EEE recovery for reuse in a distinct urban mine: a case study. <i>Detritus</i> , 15, 78-93.	Poppelaars, F., Bakker, C., & van Engelen, J. (2020). Design for divestment in a circular economy: Stimulating voluntary return of smartphones through design. <i>Sustainability</i> , 12(4), 1488.	Kim, B., Azaropantel, C., Pietrzak-David, M., & Maussion, P. (2019). Life cycle assessment for a solar energy system based on reuse components for developing countries. <i>Journal of cleaner production</i> , 208, 1459-1468.	Coughlan, D., Fitzpatrick, C., & McMahon, M. (2018). Repurposing end of life notebook computers from consumer WEEE as thin client computers—A hybrid end of life strategy for the Circular Economy in electronics. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 192, 809-820.	Arp, H. P. H., Morin, N. A., Hale, S. E., Okkenhaug, G., Breivik, K., & Sparrevik, M. (2017). The mass flow and proposed management of bisphenol A in selected Norwegian waste streams. <i>Waste Management</i> , 60, 775-785.

Recommendations for Action. <i>Sustainability</i> , 14(5), 2993.					
	Gavrilescu, D., Enache, A., Ibănescu, D., Teodosiu, C., & Fiore, S. (2021). Sustainability assessment of waste electric and electronic equipment management systems: Development and validation of the SUSTWEEE methodology. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 306, 127214.	Wilkinson, A., & Williams, I. (2020). Why do (W) EEE hoard? The effect of consumer behaviour on the release of home entertainment products into the circular economy. <i>Detritus</i> , 12, 18-33.			
	Boldoczki, S., Thorenz, A., & Tuma, A. (2021). Does increased circularity lead to environmental sustainability?: The case of washing machine reuse in Germany. <i>Journal of Industrial Ecology</i> , 25(4), 864-876.				

Fig.1. Number of publications per year

The environmental aspects of extending the life cycle of waste electrical and electronic equipment received the most attention in the revised articles. Also, the articles with the theme of preparing for reuse

received quite a lot of attention in the articles we analyzed. Unfortunately, there are few studies in areas related to the design of equipment or the environmental impact of waste electrical and electronic equipment.

Most of the papers have as their main topic the analysis of the challenges between variables and concepts and also to capitalize on the benefits of the circular economy.

Few articles aim to provide methodologies, indicators, guidelines or to compile practical solutions to the problems faced by the field of e-waste and electro-nice management, especially in the reuse and repair phase. So most of the publications stagnate at the theoretical level, while a small part of the attention is paid to the design of solutions and applications in the analyzed field.

Discussion and conclusions

Our review outlines the importance of activities in the reuse sector of waste electrical and electronic equipment. In order to make this sector as efficient as possible, it is necessary to regulate the activities of re-use and preparation for re-use. This waste electrical and electronic equipment has a lot of valuable materials from which secondary raw materials can be obtained. Such losses of raw materials endanger the next production of electrical and electronic equipment. The inclusion of circular economy principles in the field of electrical and electronic waste therefore leads to the most effective implementation of environmental protection.

Despite the fact that the first article chosen was from 2017, the number of publications began to increase. The circular economy has begun to grow considerably in recent years, bringing a dominant significance in vis-à-vis sustainability flows. In general, the articles have appeared in different magazines such as Sustainable Production and Consumption, Journal of Cleaner Production, Resources, Conservation & Recycling, Sustainability, Journal of Industrial Ecology Wiley, Environment International, Waste Management.

WEEE is a research and development framework in both developed and developing countries. Most of the articles aim to analyze the challenges or correlations between variables and concepts or to quantify the impacts of the circular economy. Few articles aim to provide methodologies, indicators, guidelines or to compile practical solutions to the problems faced by the field of e-waste management, especially in the reuse and repair phase.

The effective implementation of the way of prolonging the life cycle through reuse and of the legislative frameworks leads to the mitigation of the generation of waste electrical and electronic equipment even during some disturbances such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

However, this work could be a start for researchers or for legislative frameworks to understand how important it is to extend the life cycle of a product by reusing and repairing it.

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